

Key Address

(Th Key-1)

"Looking to the Future"

Presented By

Colonel Gregory Gilles, USAF
Lieutenant Colonel Jim Pierson, USA
U.S. Space Command

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

As with all organizations, it was realized that a vision for our command would help unify efforts towards a common goal or desired end state for the staff and our Components. Any effort to develop a vision, rested on the premise that a Space Vision must be fully supportive of a joint warfighting vision. Joint Vision 2010, the Joint Staff's vision for warfighting 15 years in the future, has served as this over arching umbrella. Other joint and service vision documents have also helped guide our efforts.

In order to begin development of a vision for United States Space Command, this effort was initiated over nine months ago. The basic framework was to develop possible warfighting scenarios in the 2010-2015 time frame. If the scenarios were considered to be plausible ones for future warfighting, then planning could be initiated to map out a command vision. The vision would then be mapped back to the required operational concepts, capabilities and technologies and organizational transformations.

After examining past revolutions in military affairs (RMAs) that have brought about a fundamental change in the nature of warfare, our thinking turned towards the possibility of an existing RMA. This one was to be centered around space and information systems. An operational scenario was developed that centered around information flow on future battlefields. The intent was to shift thinking towards the realm of possibilities for future warfare. The scenario was centered around the explosion of information on the battlefield. With the

advent of direct broadcast communication systems, gigahertz processors, terabyte databases, fusion software and on-line interactive databases, command and control elements across the battlespace would have such tremendous access to information that dominant battlefield awareness could be considered a reality. This capability combined with precision weapons and integrated sensor systems could allow for far term dominance on future battlefields.

A rough order of magnitude check on the feasibility of many of the required technologies needed suggests that the technologies would be available. What was missing and required were the development of operational concepts for future warfighting that would cause the various technologies and capabilities to come together.

Having developed alternative future scenarios, the next step was to try to understand what the implications for this type of warfighting environment would have for United States Space Command. Clearly, space and information systems were becoming increasingly important (possibly a center of gravity) to our warfighting capabilities. Conversely, space control was also becoming increasingly important - both in our ability to protect our assets and information as well as to deny our future adversaries access to their assets and information.

Our efforts, through the use of future scenarios are maturing into a more crystallized view of where United States Space Command needs to be in the 2010-2015 era.

Colonel Greg Gilles (USAF), U.S. Space Command, J5V, DSN 692-5910

Lieutenant Colonel Jim Pierson (USA), U.S. Space Command, J5R, DSN 692-2480

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

USSPACECOM FUTURE PLANS

Col Greg Gilles
DSN 692-5910

LTC Jim Pierson
DSN 692-2480

14 DEC 95

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

BRIEFING OUTLINE

- Purpose / Background
- RMA
- Future Information Flow
- Enabling Technologies
- Implications - Military / Space / Info
- The Path Ahead

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

PURPOSE of the JOURNEY

Explore Alternative Futures to Help Us Understand the Capabilities, Concepts and Requirements That Will Shape Our Space Vision.

Action without vision is just activity. Vision without action is just a dream. Vision and action together can change the world."

-- Anonymous

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

WHY A VISION?

NOT THIS -

BUT THIS -

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

BACKGROUND DOCUMENTS

- **JOINT**

- National Security Strategy
- National Military Strategy
- Joint Strategy Review
- Vision Force (Apr 95 - ADM Owens)
- The Emerging System of Systems - ADM Owens
- Joint Warfighting Center Future Concepts Brief
- Joint Vision 2010
- DSB Summer Study (94) - Info Architecture
- Revolution in Military Affairs (OSD - ONA)
- Sec Def Annual Report to Congress

- **ARMY**

- Force XXI Operations (TRADOC Pam 525-5)
- Space Support to Army Opns (FM 100-18)
- Space Support to Land Force Opns (TRADOC PAM 525-60)
- The Army Plan (TAP)
- GEN Sullivan's "Seeing the Elephant"
- Army Space in the 21st Century (LTG Garner brief)
- Knowledge-Based Warfare (Dr Berenson TRADOC)
- Army Digitization Master Plan
- TENCAP Master Plan

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

BACKGROUND DOCUMENTS

- **NAVY**
 - FORWARD...FROM THE SEA
 - Vision for Navia Space Strategy
 - Operational Maneuver from the Sea
 - C4I and the RMA (VADM Cebrowski)

- **AIR FORCE**
 - Global Reach, Global Power
 - Global Presence
 - AF Revolutionary Planning
 - New World Vista
 - Getting the AF into the 21st Century

- **MISCELLANEOUS**
 - Toffler's "WAR AND ANTI-WAR"
 - Revolution in Military Affairs (SAIC)
 - "Plan or Die"
 - Swartau's "Information Warfare"
 - "The Art of the Long View"

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

ORGANIZATIONS CONTACTED

<u>ORGANIZATIONS</u>	<u>NAMES</u>	<u>ORGANIZATIONS</u>	<u>NAMES</u>
OSD (ONA)	Mr Marshall, Col Barnett CAPT Fitzsimonds, Col Miller	AF / INX AF / SCXX	Lt Col Michael Col Kaplan, Lt Col Pait
DUSD (SA&TP)	Mr Klingner		Maj Ramirez
OSD C3I	Mr Sealey, Mr Sanford	AF / XON	Lt Col MacFarlane
CIO (Plans)	Lt Col Loverro, Col Hotard	AF / XOR	Brig Gen (Sel) Ward
NRO	Mr Ferryman Brig Gen Scanlan, Col Middleton Col Francisco	AF / XOXS AFSPC/CV AFSPC/XP	Lt Col Noetzel Lt Gen Caruana Maj Gen DeKok
DISA (D8)	Mr Osterholtz	AFSWC	Maj Gen Vesely
ARPA	Col Mahen	AF TENCAP Adv Group	
JS / J5	Col Graves, Col Stratton, Col Hall	SMC/SAPO	Col Watterson
JS/J6	COL Barron, CAPT Gravell		
JS / CINC LNO	Col Spiker		
C2 JWCA	Lt Col Green		
DIA	Mr Shackleford, Col Roe, Mr Dunleavy, Mr Eldridge		
JWC	Mr Comstock, Lt Col Lehnert,	N63 (Space & EW)	CAPT Thompson/Roeting
DCSOPS / SSP	Lt Col Felker	N513	CDR Bouchard
TRADOC	COL Laney	NAVSPACECOM	Col Garbrous, Dr Springer
ARSPACE	Dr Berenson, COL Hartman		
Army DigitizationOff	COL Kulbacki, Mr Marrs, Mr Baker LTC Cox		

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

ORGANIZATIONS CONTACTED

ORGANIZATIONS NAMES

OAD	Mr Poturalski, Mr Schultz
Booz Allen	Dr Rich, Mr Buhl, Mr Stephens
Nat'l Correlation Working Group	RADM (ret) March, Maj Gen (ret) Larsen
Olin Chair (USAFSA)	Gen (ret) McCarthy
USSPACECOM	UD, J2, J5, J6, J2V, J3V, J5V, NSA LNO, NAVSPACECOM Det, IAWG, J2 Working Group, N/SPJ6C
PACOM	DCINC, DEP J5, J3, J6

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

REVOLUTION IN MILITARY AFFAIRS

- **New Technologies + Operational Changes + Organizational Changes**
- Fundamental change in the nature of warfare
- Characterized more by the magnitude than the pace of change
- Enabled by technologies but driven by operational needs and shortfalls in existing or projected capabilities
- Examples of past RMA's:
 - advent of gunpowder
 - France's "levee en masse"
 - 19th century industrialization
 - mechanization of warfare
 - nuclear weapons
 - stealth
 -
 -
 -
 - **space and information systems ??**

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

IS THERE A NEW RMA ?

- Transition to a **“System of Systems”**
 - Advanced C4I / Battlefield Awareness
 - Precision Strike
 - Sensors (ISR)
- **Key Elements**
 - Digitization
 - Computer Processing
 - GPS
- **Accept near term RISK for far term DOMINANCE ???**

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

HOW DOES USSPACECOM FIT WITHIN THE DoD VISION?

' LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

DoD Vision => Joint Vision 2010

- Dominant Maneuver
- Precision Strike
- Operational Protection
- Integrated Logistics

Full Spectrum
Dominance

What Does This Mean to Space?

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

Fundamental Elements of Information

- Key questions from a Warrior's perspective (Cushman's Catechism):
 - Where am I?
 - Where is the enemy?
 - What is the enemy doing?
 - How fast is the enemy moving?
 - How long will it take him to _____?
 - What forces / assets do I have to kill / neutralize the enemy?
 - Where are my forces / assets?
 - Are my forces / assets in balance?
- These questions apply across the spectrum of conflict

TACTICAL SCENARIO in 2005/2010/2015

- **Setting**
 - C2 element (JTF - Corps thru Company level) in active combat zone
 - GBS receive terminal (24-96 Mbps) & LDR (2.4k -9.6Kbps) EHF LPI / LPD Transmitter
- **Situation**
 - C2 element receives alert of threat 20-30 kms away
 - Display of tgt type, precise location, assignable over-the-horizon weapon systems, time-to-target, pk, recommended weapon system (w/current status)
 - C2 element selects weapon, coordinates digitally (if required), and transmits LPI / LPD msg
 - Weapons system receives request and engages with “cheap” smart weapon
 - Real-Time/Near Real-Time BDA transmitted to all levels of command
 - Elapsed time 5 - 10 minutes

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

INFORMATION FLOW in 2015

GBS

24 - 96 Mbps

- High Volume Intel
- C2
- Force Status / Guidance
- Threat Picture

• ATOs/ROE / BDA

- Logistics / Medical
- Wpns Status

Characteristics:

- GBS receive terminal
- EHF LPI/LPD terminal
- Small, cheap multi-terabyte data base
- Gigahertz processors
- Fusion software
- On-line, interactive data bases
- Proliferated throughout Theater
 - Multi-level Info security
 - High volume data management / control

EHF LPI/LPD

2.4 - 9.6 Kbps

- Weapons release
- Unit status
- Requests for update
- Database status
- Tasking

Smart "push" or "pull"

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

ENABLING / EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES

<u>Technology</u>	<u>1995</u>	<u>2015</u>
Direct Broadcast Satellites	Avail	Common
Small, Cheap Terabyte Databases	Not avail	Likely
Small, Cheap Gigahertz Processors	Becoming Avail	Common
Small, Cheap LPI/LPD Receivers/Antennas	Not Avail	Likely
Affordable, High Capacity EHF Satellites	Not Avail	Likely
Worldwide, High Precision GPS Grid	Not Avail	Likely
"Fool-Proof" Multi Level Data Security	Unknown	Unknown
NRT SIGINT Processing	Avail	Common
NRT IMINT Processing / Exploitation	Not Avail	Likely
Affordable Smart Weapons	Not Avail	Likely
High Volume Data Management / Control	Not Avail	Likely
High Capacity Interactive Data Bases	Not Avail	Likely
Data Fusion (AI, Neural Nets, Correlation)	Very Limited	Likely

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

IMPLICATIONS for the MILITARY, SPACE and INFORMATION OPERATIONS

- Highly lethal combat zone
- Transition to a capabilities-based force from a threat-based force
 - Commercial technologies will lead DoD
 - DoD must leverage / target limited R&D dollars smartly
- Space / Information systems becoming increasingly important to U.S. deterrent and warfighting capabilities
 - NRT situational awareness
 - Unique advantage / vulnerability for the U.S.
- Other countries recognizing importance of Space / Information systems
 - Build their own / use others'
 - Disrupt / deny / degrade / destroy our systems

IMPLICATIONS for the MILITARY, SPACE and INFORMATION OPERATIONS

- **Space / Information control of growing importance**
 - Disrupt / deny / degrade / destroy enemy systems
 - Protect our assets
- **Information revolution may significantly alter existing military organizations**
- **Rising powers (niche competitors) may leapfrog U.S. in selected technical areas**

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

IMPLICATIONS for the MILITARY, SPACE and INFORMATION OPERATIONS

- **Advanced C4I will be the key to dominant battlespace awareness**
 - Long transition time for space segment implementation of GBS (start now - major cultural change leading to org/oper'l changes)
 - Protect critical comm / intel nodes
 - Develop advanced EHF system (MILSTAR too costly / inadequate)
 - Assure U.S. (deny adversary) GPS access
 - Develop time phased approach to space segment security
 - Develop higher speed Intel processing systems
 - Develop high volume interactive / integrated data base management / control
 - Develop data fusion capability to handle massive flow of data
 - Maintain C4I flexibility to accommodate diverse military situations
 - Integrate space with other mediums (air, ground and sea)

WHERE DO WE GO FROM HERE?

- **Get on-board the visionary bandwagon**
 - Participate in OSD/Joint Staff visionary projects
 - Monitor Service visionary projects
- **Analyze USSPACECOM missions**
- **Establish a USSPACECOM vision (based upon mission)**
- **Use the vision (“downboard thinking” - chess strategy)**
 - Promulgate to components
 - Use for Strategy / Doctrine / Organization / Architecture / IPL / Investment Strategy / POM / BES / Testimony
- **Institutionalize through classical strategy / goals / objectives techniques throughout command**

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

TRANSLATING VISION TO CAPABILITIES

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE

CONTINUING AREAS OF CONCERN

- Gaps in real time IMINT / SIGINT / MASINT
- GPS signal availability / denial
- Data / info integrity (corruption / viruses / destruction)
- Critical node security (destruction / interruption)
- Satellite vulnerabilities (not near term)
- Information warfare (not directed at space systems, but ...)
- Spectrum availability / congestion (assured access / frequency independence)
- Information Security (using our info against us)
-
-
- Weapons of mass destruction

LOOKING TO THE FUTURE